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ABSTRACT

Noise, vibration and harshness (NVH), in addition to safety and cost, have become important factors in the definition of vehicle quality as a result of the market's search for an increasing refinement. Although noise emissions are a negative side effect of almost all technical innovation developments, determining the specific descriptive factors of vehicle interior acoustics is a serious challenge for researchers and manufacturers because unlike many systems, vehicles have a large number of sources of vibration and noise, continuous and transient, which are interdependent and also depend on factors of a subjective nature. This paper aims to provide knowledge about theory and the best techniques for determining the specific descriptive factors of vehicle interior acoustics, as well as a numerical model for their determination followed by the presentation of experimentally obtained results so that they can make informed judgments about strategies for NVH solutions at an early stage of vehicle development.

KEYWORDS: NVH, vehicle interior acoustics, determining specific descriptive factors, strategies for NVH, numerical model for acoustics factors.

1. INTRODUCTION

Noise, vibration and harshness (NVH) are defining factors in vehicle quality and design, especially in terms of refinement. The problem of vibrations is closely related to reliability and quality, while the problem of noise has become increasingly important for vehicle passengers and from an environmental point of view. Harsh, which is strictly related to the quality and transient nature of vibration and noise, is also closely related to the refinement of the vehicle. The acoustic descriptive factors of vehicle interiors represent a serious and current challenge for manufacturers and researchers in the field of acoustics.

In recent years, the trend has been increasing towards vehicle designs that compromise mass and higher engine speeds, which is a prominent source of noise. The values of the interior acoustic pressure level in vehicles increase the higher the engine speed, which is a continuous source of noise on board vehicles. Moreover, the emergence of electric and hybrid vehicles has tended to increase the potential for noise and vibration from non-engine sources, presenting many new problems for automotive engineers. These developments also coincided with a reduction in time to market for new vehicles, which created an increased reliance on computer-aided design and analysis, and existing or newly designed mathematical models with less time prototype testing [1].

This accelerated development of new and highly refined vehicles is additive of the presence of accurate numerical analyses of vehicle interior acoustics and noise sources and the effects of on-board vibrations on the human factor and calls for the improvement of mathematical models and analytical techniques. While NVH analysis has in recent years been aided by the evolution of finite element and multibody systems analysis software, there is still a fundamental need to improve the mathematical models that take into account both subjective and objective factors in vibration analysis and which also underlie design software [2].

Noise emissions in vehicles is also a negative side effect of almost all technical innovations, as a result of the evolution of the vehicle from a simple mechanism to a complex dynamic system. Thus noise inside vehicles is therefore an unavoidable problem in the vehicle industry. However, not being considered, noise measurements

and the determination of descriptive factors of vehicle interior acoustics, with the aim of noise reduction are generally identified as a source of additional costs [3].

Exposure to noise pollution is constantly increasing, in some countries it is considered an occupational disease. Even in highly developed countries, traffic noise has increased by 0.2–0.3 dB(A) per year, despite increasingly stringent regulations having low L_w emission power levels of cars, motorcycles and trucks in Europe on average 6, 9, respectively 12 dB(A) in the last 20 years. Decisive the emission level is increasing, especially due to the increasingly heavy traffic grid of streets, roads and highways. Air traffic noise disturbances developed similarly: successful noise reduction (ΔL) at individual sources (L_w) were more than counterbalanced worldwide by their increasing numbers (n). According to the public information of the Federal Environment Agency, the number of people suffering from noise exposure pollution in the world has doubled by the year 2023 [4].

$$L = L_w + 10 \lg n \quad (i) \quad [5]$$

The most prominent sources of noise for the human body

Road traffic is one of the most prominent sources of noise in the EU. It has been estimated that 100 million people live in areas where traffic noise levels exceed 55 dB and approximately 32 million people are exposed to levels above 65 dB. The second most prominent source of noise is railways, with 19 million people exposed to levels greater than 55 dB. The third largest source is airports, with 4.1 million people affected. The fourth largest source is industrial noise, which affects about 1 million people [6].

The most common harmful effects on the human body as a result of exposure to noise levels

The most common problem caused by noise pollution is hearing loss. In addition to this harmful effect, the prominent noise level causes breathing problems, high blood pressure and pulse, headaches, gastritis and heart attacks, but also stress, depression, anxiety, hysteria, fatigue (also applicable to animals), noises greater than 45 dB cause sleep problems (maximum recommended intensity is 30 dB), aggression and restlessness and have an effect on cognitive functions (memory problems, concentration disorders)[7].

The most common harmful effects on the human body as a result of exposure to noise levels

The noise level within the threshold of audibility of the human auditory organ and which is accepted depending on the exposure period of the human body according to research in the field are shown in the figure above [8].

The recommended noise level for the human body

The random variations, known as noise accepted by the human auditory organ, have the values observed in the adjacent graph. Therefore, noise is the source of producing a series of health problems, such as: communication and concentration difficulties; stress and irritability; sleep disorders; cardiovascular problems and negative effects on the endocrine system, on performance, work capacity and social behavior. Officially, in many countries hearing loss at work is considered an occupational disease. Even short periods of noise exposure of the human body can

have negative effects on human health. These effects also apply to drivers, who, according to the worldwide statistics to date, spend an average of up to 60 min a day in their vehicles [8].

Statistical data on time spent in vehicles

From year to year the time spent in vehicles is increasing, the vehicle being the main means of transport used by the population. Determining the methods of evaluating the acoustics of the passenger compartment are essential to achieve the acoustic comfort experienced by the passengers [9].

Acoustic comfort is one of the essential factors, established by consumers. There are also marketing factors, from the point of view of the vehicle manufacturers, because the differences, at the present time, between the different models in the same market segment are becoming more and more difficult to establish in terms of performance and aesthetics, the difference being made by the comfort level. The comfort experienced by passengers inside vehicles, in particular, and in a certain environment, in general, is characterized by a subjective side, because it is constant that it is a considerable variation of different people in the same situation (subjective factors were identified as: temperature, air quality, light intensity, noise, vibrations, etc.). Therefore, the first step in making any assessment is to eliminate the various types of external stimuli that are considered sources of discomfort [10].

The objective of this study is to address the problem of interior noise in vehicles, by presenting a numerical analysis model of the acoustics of the vehicle interior that is based on standardized acoustic emission factors taking into account the volume of the vehicle, speed, road configuration, distance from the receiver. In this way, important conclusions are obtained regarding the level of noise emissions in the passenger compartment of motor vehicles. Also the paper presents a monitoring and measurement strategy as well as important data regarding the acoustics of the vehicle interior, together with the selection of the best available techniques, with the aim of contributing to the further mitigation of the potential sound impact on passengers, as well as the implementation of a strategy that leads to improve the indoor acoustic comfort level.

2. FUNDAMENTALS OF VEHICLE INTERIOR ACOUSTICS

An understanding of acoustic fundamentals is essential in noise control and interpretation of the noise criterion present in the passenger compartment of vehicles. This section outlines some of the basic principles of the propagation of sound inside the vehicles, from the various prominent noise sources on board the vehicles, to the receivers, which are the passengers. Sound is transmitted from a source to a receiver through an elastic medium called way. In a vehicle engineering context, this is the surrounding air or the vehicle body structure, the latter giving rise to the term structured sound [11].

The simplest form of sound propagation occurs when a small sphere is pulsating harmonic in free space (away from any bounding surfaces). The vibration the surface of the sphere causes the air molecules in contact with it to vibrate and that the vibration is transmitted radially outward to adjacent air molecules. This produces a propagating wave having a characteristic speed c , i.e. the speed of sound in the air. At an arbitrary point along the path, the air is under pressure fluctuations that overlap the ambient pressure. A sound source vibrating at a frequency f , produces sound at this frequency. Taking a snapshot instantaneous pressure and travel far from the source, the variation of pressure with distance is also sinusoidal. The distance between the pressure peaks is constant and known as wavelength λ . This is related to c and f by the equation [12]:

$$\lambda = \frac{c}{f} \quad (\text{ii})$$

This equation shows that as the frequency increases, the wavelength decreases (since c is constant for the given atmospheric conditions). In the audible range of 20 Hz to 20 kHz, the wavelength varies correspondingly from 17 m to 17 mm.

The propagation speed c is given by [13]:

$$c = \sqrt{\frac{p\gamma}{\rho}} = \sqrt{\gamma RT} \quad (\text{iii})$$

where p = the ambient pressure, ρ = corresponding density of the medium, γ = ratio of specific heats for air, R = universal gas constant and T = absolute temperature. For air at standard atmospheric pressure and 20 °C, the magnitude of c is 343 m/s.

Table 1. Velocity of wave propagation in various media [13]

Medium	c (m/s)
Air at 1 bar and 20°C	343
Mild steel	5050
Aluminum	5000
Vulcanized rubber	1269
Water at 15°C	1440
Iron	5130
Glass	5600
Platinum	2800
Zinc	4500
Copper	3600

The property of an acoustic wave to oppose a medium to its propagation is called acoustic impedance. It is defined as the ratio between the sound pressure p and particle speed u . The relationship that defines acoustic impedance is [13]:

$$z = \frac{p}{u} = \rho c \quad (\text{iv})$$

For standard air pressure and temperature (101.3 kPa and 20 °C), z is equal to 415 rayls (Ns/m³).

Acoustic Intensity, I , is defined as the time averaged rate of transport of acoustic energy by a wave per unit area normal to the wavefront. The equation for defining sound intensity is [13]:

$$I = \frac{p_{rms}^2}{\rho c} \quad (\text{v})$$

p_{rms} is the r.m.s. pressure fluctuation. For a harmonic wave, $p_{rms} = \frac{\hat{p}}{\sqrt{2}}$, where $\hat{p}$ is the peak pressure.

Therefore [13]:

$$I = \frac{\hat{p}^2}{2\rho c} \quad (\text{vi})$$

Certain reference quantities are used for sound emission measurements. For sound transmission in air, the reference r.m.s. pressure is taken to be $p_{ref} = 20$ IPa which corresponds approximately to the threshold of hearing at the reference frequency of 1 kHz. With a reference impedance $z_{ref} = (\rho c)_{ref} = 400$ rayls, the reference intensity $I_{ref} = 10^{-12} \text{ W/m}^2$ from Eq. (v). Since the acoustic power is the intensity times area, from a reference spherical area $A_{ref} = 1 \text{ m}^2$, the reference sound power is 10^{-12} W [13].

The human ear is capable of detecting acoustic quantities in a very wide range, for instance, pressure variations from $\mu 20$ Pa to 100 Pa. The conversion of the sound measured by the measuring instruments to be comparable to that perceived by the human ear is done by weighting scales. This is achieved by using the decibel scale. The

quantity of interest x is expressed as $10 \log_{10}(x/x_{ref})$, where both x and x_{ref} have units of power. Using the reference quantities above, the sound power level (L_w), sound intensity level (L_i) and sound pressure level (L_p) in decibels (dB) are as follows [13]:

$$L_w = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{w}{w_{ref}} \right) \quad (\text{vii})$$

$$L_i = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{i}{i_{ref}} \right) \quad (\text{viii})$$

$$L_p = 10 \log_{10} \frac{p^2}{p_{ref}^2} = 20 \log \frac{p}{p_{ref}} \quad (\text{ix})$$

When it is noted that the threshold of hearing corresponds to a sound pressure level of 0 dB, it may be shown that for standard temperature and pressure (101.3 kPa and 20 °C), L_w , L_i and L_p in dB are related as follows:

$$L_i = L_p - 0.16 \quad (\text{x})$$

$$L_w = L_p + 20 \log_{10} \frac{r}{r_{ref}} - 0.16 \quad (\text{xi})$$

where $r_{ref} = 0.282$ m for the reference spherical area $A_{ref} = 1 \text{m}^2$. From Eq. (x), it is seen that L_p and L_i are approximately equal numerically, while Eq. (xi) is useful for determining the sound power level of an acoustic source from sound pressure level measurements in free field conditions. For these whole field radiation conditions, the reduction in sound pressure level with every doubling of radial distance from the source is 6 dB.

It is often necessary to determine the sound pressure level of two or more uncorrelated sound sources when the level for each source is known. This can be achieved by using the Eq.(xii) [13]:

$$L_{p,total} \approx L_{i,total} = 10 \log_{10} (\sum 10^{0.1L_{pi}}) \quad (\text{xii})$$

When an incident wave strikes a reflecting surface, the wave is reflected back towards the source. In the vicinity of the reflecting surface, the incident and reflected waves interact to produce what is known as a reverberant field. The depth of this field is dependent on the absorptive properties of the reflecting surface. A typical interaction between incident and reflected waves is shown in figure below and sound pressure level variations as function of distance "r" from the sound source are as shown in figure below:

Interaction of incident and reflected waves [13]

Sound pressure level as a function of distance from a simple spherical source [13]

Various practical situations arise when the sound source is positioned close to a hard reflecting surface. The following are idealized situations:

- Whole-space radiation—when there are no reflecting surfaces, i.e. the source is in free space.
- Half-space radiation—when the source is at the center of a flat hard (reflecting) surface, e.g. the sound source is on a floor.
- Quarter space radiation—when the source is at the intersection of two flat hard surfaces which are perpendicular to one another, e.g. the sound source is on a floor next to a wall.
- Eighth space radiation—when the source is positioned at the intersection of three flat perpendicular hard surfaces, e.g. the sound source is in a corner.

Increasing the number and proximity of reflecting surfaces to a source increases the acoustic intensity. The situations described above can be represented by the directivity index DI expressed in terms of the directivity factor Q [13]:

$$DI = 10 \log_{10} Q \quad (\text{xiii})$$

- For a whole space $Q = 1$ (DI = 0 dB)
- For a half space $Q = 2$ (DI = 3 dB)
- For a quarter space $Q = 4$ (DI = 6 dB)
- For an eighth space $Q = 8$ (DI = 9 dB).

The sound power level (PWL) of a source located in any of the positions described above can be calculated from sound pressure level (SPL) measurements using a modified form of Eq. (xi) as follows:

$$L_w = L_p + 20 \log_{10} \frac{r}{r_{ref}} - DI - 0.16 \quad (\text{xiv}) \quad [13]$$

3. SOUND IN VEHICLE INTERIORS

The air inside the enclosed volume of a vehicle cabin behaves as an elastic fluid and consequently has a number of natural frequencies and modes (standing waves). For a simple rectangular box, these frequencies and mode shapes can be readily calculated. However, the cabin space of a typical car is far more complex in shape e.g. there are intrusions such as seats and there are numerous types of surface having different (acoustic) absorption characteristics. These make the acoustic natural frequencies and modes extremely difficult to determine. On board the vehicle there are a number of prominent sources of noise (the engine and its auxiliary systems, the exhaust system, the HVAC system, the interaction of the relay track with the vehicle's propulsion system, the interaction of the vehicle with the outside environment-air, etc.) [14], generators of sounds propagating in the passenger compartment. The measurement of vehicle interior noise is required for a variety of dictating purposes the need for a series of measuring equipment. In development work there is a the requirement for measuring continuous noise levels such as that from the roadway and their auxiliaries; there are also requirements

for component noise testing determine sound output power, frequency analysis and source identification. Even for type approval of vehicles there are requirements for the noise assessment of the entire vehicle. Next, a database is presented regarding the cumulative estimate of the noise level inside vehicles of different configurations and types, classified in accordance with RNTR 1 (road vehicle, off-road car, minibus, bus, VAN-type cargo vehicle and truck), monitored stationary and in motion for various engine operating speeds.

Interior sound pressure values in vehicles of different configurations, monitored stationary

The sound pressure level was obtained experimentally, with the engine running, stationary and the system HVAC off. The tests were carried out for 3000 rpm, 2000 rpm and 1000 rpm for each vehicle. The tests were carried out on flat ground, and at a distance of 20 m there were no opaque objects or buildings that could influence sound propagation. The average values of the sound pressure level ($Leq(A)$), weighted in the weighting class A, can be seen in the graph above, in dB, on the OX axis of the graph. The equipment required for the measurements was: PC system (laptop), Sound analysis software, Sound level meter (SLM), accuracy class 1, with weighting in frequency and time, according to the specifications of international standards, such as IEC 61672 – 1, instrument (of usually portable) that is designed to measure sound pressure levels in a standardized way. It responds to sound in roughly the same way as the human ear and provides objective, reproducible measurements of sound pressure levels. A sound level meter comprises a microphone, a preamplifier, signal processing and a display. The microphone converts the acoustic signal into an equivalent electrical signal. The most suitable type of microphone for sound level meters is the condenser microphone, which combines precision with stability and reliability. The electrical signal initially produced by the microphone being very low is then amplified by a preamplifier before entering the main processor. Signal processing includes frequency and time weighting as specified by international standards such as IEC 61672 – 1. At the beginning and at the end of each series of measurements, the entire acoustic measurement system shall be checked by means of an acoustic calibration device that complies with the requirements for acoustic calibration devices of accuracy class 1 according to standard IEC 60942:2003. Without any other adjustment, the difference between readings must be less than or equal to 0.5 dB. If this value is exceeded, the measurement results obtained at the last satisfactory previous check are not considered valid. The meteorological measuring instruments are positioned in close proximity to the driver, at a height of $1,2 \text{ m} \pm 0,02 \text{ m}$ from the driver's seat. The measurements are carried out when the ambient air temperature is between $+ 5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $+ 40 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ [14].

No tests have been performed if, when measuring noise, the wind speed, including gusts, at the height of the microphone exceeds 5 m/s.

Diagram of sound pressure level values inside vehicles of different configurations, at different engine operating speeds, monitored stationary

The values obtained according to the experimental determinations fall within the reference lines of the average values of 65.75 dB for 1000 rpm, 69.81 for 2000 rpm and 70.14 for 3000 rpm.

Interior sound pressure values in vehicles of different configurations, monitored in motion, at speed 50 km/h

Based on the same test methodology, interior sound pressure level values were determined for the same stationary tested vehicles. The speed at which the measurements were made was 50 km/h.

Diagram of the values of the acoustic pressure level in the passenger compartment at 50 km/h

Diagram of sound pressure level values inside vehicles of different configurations, at different engine operating speeds, monitored in motion

The indoor sound pressure level values, determined with a precision class 1 sound level meter, can be viewed in the graph above. The highest values of the acoustic pressure level (Leq(A)), in motion at 50 km/h, were obtained in the case of the truck, with a value of 88.7 dB(A).

4. CONCLUSION

This paper presents a database regarding the realization of cumulative preliminary estimates for the level of interior noise in vehicles of different categories, monitored stationary and in motion, in order to obtain an initial picture of the cumulative impact due to noise and vibrations generated by acoustic sources originating from the operation of vehicles. At the same time, the work is based on a numerical acoustic analysis of the vehicle interior.

At the same time, a monitoring and measurement strategy is presented as well as important data on the acoustics of the vehicle cabin with the aim of helping vehicle manufacturers and researchers in selecting the best available techniques, with the aim of contributing to the further mitigation of the potential sound impact on passengers, as well as the implementation of a strategy to improve the indoor acoustic comfort level.

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